

ILLUMINATION OF SOCIAL PROTECTION SYSTEMS IN THE
WORKS OF SCHOLARS

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Annotatsiya. Muallif maqolada allomalarining nogironligi bo‘lgan shaxslarning islom huquqshunosligida, sharqona tarbiyada, davlat boshqaruvidagi juda katta e‘tibor berilganini ko‘rishimiz mumkin.

Kalit so‘zlar. Hidoya, podshoh, fiqh, ulamo, faqir, miskin, olim, mukotib, qarzdor, xalq, asar.

Аннотация. В статье автора мы видим, что большое внимание людям с ограниченными возможностями уделяется в исламском правоведении, восточном образовании, государственном управлении.

Ключевые слова. Хидая, король, юриспруденция, учёный, бедняк, бедняк, учёный, лауреат, должник, нация, работа.

Annotation. In the author's article, we can see that a lot of attention is given to people with disabilities in Islamic jurisprudence, oriental education, and public administration.

Keywords. Hidayat, king, jurisprudence, scholar, poor, scholar, honoree, debtor, nation, work.

The attitude towards persons with disabilities is formed based on the historical development process of each country and the specific mentality of the people. The level of justice in any society is measured by the level of attention, living conditions, and well-being created for people with disabilities living in that country.

For example, a felon charged with a felony or misdemeanor is granted disability relief. It is said that "Sabi", wifehood, slavery, insanity, blindness, illness, and disbelief of the Zimmi are not taken into account, that is, a Sab'i (young child), a grown man, a

man is a woman." , a freed person, a sane person, a healthy person, a blind person with open eyes, a sick person (whose arm or leg is amputated) are killed by a person with all their limbs, in all cases, the killer will be avenged (o 'led). The shortcomings of the above killings are negligible” [1].

And it is said that "A speechless person's taking a wife, getting divorced, selling his property, buying something, and clearly writing and pointing out about revenge are considered equal to his speech. 2. However, if he confesses to a deed at the level of punishment, such as insults, adultery, theft, by writing or gesture, then the mute person will not be punished and his hand will not be cut off. Because confession is doubt. Doubt is not punishable. 3. Scholars have said about a person who is dumb to the point of not being able to speak: "Even if the stuttering of the language is prolonged, if the signs are understood, the dispositions in matters such as marriage, divorce, sales, and the writing of the proof of revenge are considered as if the sign is taken into account by a person who is speechless. is taken into account" [2].

There are seven categories of people to whom it is given in addition to obligatory alms such as zakat, ushr al-fitr, nazr: 1) the poor, 2) the needy, 3) the scholar, 4) the honored, 5) the debtor, 6) the one who deviates from the path of God, the stranger [3].

Termizli is considered to be both a student and a companion of the famous Muhaddith, Abu Isa al-Tirmizi was a student of al-Bukhari, and in his Sahih Termizi complex, Hazrat Rasulullah said: "To laugh at the face of your brother is a charity for you, and to give him good commandments and evil deeds is a charity." , it is charity for you to clearly show something to a blind person, it is charity for you to remove a stone, thorn and bone from the road, it is charity for you to pour water from your bucket to someone else's bucket"[4].

Al Farabi was the first to create a doctrine about the origin, goals and tasks of society in the conditions of the Middle Ages. This doctrine covers many issues of social life, state management, education, morals, enlightenment, religious beliefs, war and reconciliation, labor, and others. In his work entitled "The City of Virtuous People", Farabi emphasizes the right to work of people with disabilities and the need for their

economic support by the state. As it is written, "Justice is expressed first of all in the correct distribution of the good things that belong to all the inhabitants of the city and in the full preservation of the wealth of those who are distributed. These are good things, riches, health, respect, ranks and other such things, of which each one should have his share, and it is unjust to take more or less. If he gets a little, it is unfair to the person, if he gets a lot, it is unfair to the people. That is, it is unfair to others. Everyone who receives his share must take care of it. It is wrong to use this share in a way that does not benefit either oneself or the people" [5].

Therefore, there are no poor people in a virtuous state. But there may be persons with disabilities and patients. Funds for their provision should be allocated from the state treasury. As far as possible, it is necessary to involve them in useful work,[6] it is emphasized in Farabi's ideas.

"In a virtuous state, everyone, even people with disabilities (as long as they have the strength) should be engaged in work suitable to their art. It is necessary for everyone to do only one trade or one job." It can be thought that this idea arose under the influence of Plato. According to Plato, everything can be done in greater quantity, better and easier, if any work is done in accordance with one's natural abilities, at the right time, without being distracted by other work. The state does not force its population to do a lot of work for three reasons: 1) not every person is suitable for doing any work and profession, it is necessary to assign work according to ability and specialization; 2) if a person is constantly engaged in a job or profession, he will improve, become knowledgeable and skilled in his field; 3) due to the need to complete many tasks within a certain period, combining two tasks prevents them from being completed on time[7].

Nasir Khisrav's works also contain many works of universal importance. Another of the universal spiritual values in the sage's work are high ideas and advices such as being fair and honest to others, showing mercy to the poor and weak, and forgiving the sins of others. The great poet appeals to officials with the same spirit of appeal, writing

verses urging them to be compassionate and kind to the working people under their command [8].

For example, Ahmad Donish's "Nawadir ul-Waqae", Mahmud Ibn Vali's "Bahr ul-asrar fi manoqib ul-ahyor" ("The sea of secrets about the glory of noble people"), Mir Muhammad Amin Bukhari's "Ubaidullanama", Muhammad Yusuf Munshi's "Tarikhi Muqimkhani", "Shajarai Turk" by Abdulghazi Bahadirkhan, "Dastur ul-muluk" by Khoja Samandar Termizi, "Muhit ut-tawarikh" by Muhammad Amin Bukhari, "History of Amir lashkar Alimqul" by Mulla Yunusjon Munshi [9] special attention was paid to their caring relations with vulnerable sections of the population, in particular with persons with disabilities.

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